

Life history and reproduction of *Nothobranchius* fishes

Béla Nagy

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The biological life cycle, reproductive behavior and egg development of *Nothobranchius* species is perfectly adapted to the special conditions of the seasonal biotopes in which they occur. The adult fish deposit eggs into the muddy substrate of the habitat where they survive the dry season while undergoing development with intervening rest periods (Skelton, 2001; Watters, 2009). Since the survival of the population must be secured during the relatively brief period of a single rainy season, the eggs must be ready to hatch when the rains arrive and the habitat fills with water. The development of the fish is then very rapid in order to reach sexual maturity in the shortest time.

Nothobranchius species are characterized by the following traits: relatively small adult size; adaptation to unstable climatic and environmental conditions; produce large numbers of eggs to ensure a potentially adequate number of offspring; no parental care and protection of the offspring; and a low ability to compete, with most offspring dying before reaching reproductive age.

Rapid growth and early sexual maturation

In nature there is, normally, plenty of food available for the newly-hatched fry. Tiny organisms, which serve as food for the fish, also survive the dry season in some way and quickly re-populate the recently formed temporary biotopes. The habitats, usually still expanding in size at the time the fry hatch, provide enough living space for the development of the newly-hatched fish. The period of growth is, however, limited and depends on the length of the rainy season and on the period when the habitat holds a sufficient volume of water (Watters, 2009). Given their seasonal nature, the habitats will be capable of hosting the adult *Nothobranchius* for a limited period only and, consequently, conditions dictate that the fish grow rapidly and reach an early reproductive stage (Valdesalici & Cellerino, 2003; Cellerino *et al.*, 2015). The growth rate might vary to some extent on an interspecific level, as a result of long-term climatic conditions in a given area, but the growth of the fish is invariably rapid. When

relatively slow growth does occur it is usually due to unfavourable conditions in the habitat, such as the limited availability of food, a situation that can be exacerbated by unusually dense populations. The adult lifespan of particular *Nothobranchius* species will depend on regional rainfall patterns but under optimal conditions most can be sexually mature in three to four weeks from hatching. At that stage the fishes will not yet have attained their full size but will continue to grow until the end of their lives. Reproduction is, however, an energetically demanding exercise, especially for the females, so growth rate may slow down after sexual maturity has been reached (Haas, 1976; Cellerino *et al.*, 2015).

Intra-population growth differences can also be observed. Some individuals within a population will grow at a relatively fast rate, providing those individuals with an advantage under exceptionally harsh conditions, when a given habitat dries up again soon after the start of the rainy season, and the most rapidly growing specimens would be the ones to establish the next generation. The author has, on a number of occasions, noted that some seasonal habitats that were on the verge of drying out completely, hosted only very young *Nothobranchius* specimens. However, the fish were starting to show some signs of sexual maturity and may have already begun laying the first eggs. At least, they started to breed not very long after they were collected and placed in captivity (Nagy, 2008).

Intense growth rates do, however, result in shorter lifespans and those specimens that mature earlier may live for a shorter time than those that grew relatively slowly. Consequently, the slower growing

specimens may inhabit the biotope for a longer time and may, therefore, contribute to a greater extent to the reproductive process, if favourable conditions allow the habitat to exist for a relatively long time (Nagy and Horváth Kis, 2010).

Habitat use

It can often be observed in the natural biotopes that females and males inhabit different parts of the same habitat. Males typically show territorial behaviour and protect suitable spawning sites, such as areas with a thick mud base or an embayment protected by vegetation. The author often found the largest, most dominant males in those parts of the biotope where the eggs had the best protection in a deep layer of mud and the fish had protection from predators. In these cases the females inhabited either the more open central parts of the habitat or were hiding in the dense vegetation.

At many locations it happens that several *Nothobranchius* species can be found in the same habitat. This is especially common in the coastal region of Tanzania. The males of the different species will usually have very different coloration and body shape and it is easy to distinguish between them. The females will also show some distinguishing features, such as small differences in body or fin shape, and a pattern of darker markings on the body and fins (e.g. spots or faint cross-bar markings). These features allow the males to identify the females. In the case of several species co-inhabiting the same site, usually each species would occupy a different niche of the biotope. Observations by the author indicate that males and females of the same species

tend to stay in close proximity to each other when several species are present in the same pool. For example, in an ephemeral pool near the Mbezi River, in the coastal region of Tanzania, the author found four species in the same habitat (Figures 1–5) (Nagy, 2010b). *Nothobranchius melanospilus*, the largest, was abundant and inhabited the central, open part of the biotope. Only a single trio of *N. ruudwildekampi* could be collected, in an embayment covered by leaves. Only one pair of *N. albimarginatus* was found in another embayment on the opposite side of the pool. Several specimens of *N. luekei*, both males and females, were found at one side of the biotope only, where it was overgrown by dense thorny vegetation. Interestingly,

during a second visit to the same locality three weeks later, the pool was slightly smaller and of the four species only *N. luekei* was found, again among thorny vegetation (Nagy and Horváth Kis, 2010). Incidentally, a previous group found *N. rubripinnis*, as well as the above-mentioned species at this particular site, making a total of five *Nothobranchius* co-existing in the habitat (Watters, pers. comm.). The *N. rubripinnis* occupied the same habitat niches as *N. albimarginatus* and *N. luekei*.

Specific habitat preference may be shown by different species that occur in the same general area but not generally in the same body of water (i.e. sympatric but not syntopic). In Uganda, *N. robustus* and *N. ugandensis* live in habitats that, in general,

Figure 1: Locality Mbezi River TZN 09-9 where the author collected four different species of *Nothobranchius* - *N. melanospilus*, *N. albimarginatus*, *N. ruudwildekampi* and *N. luekei*, and where a fifth species, *N. rubripinnis*, is also known to occur. Each occupy a different niche of the biotope.

differ in water chemistry and ecology. *N. robustus* tends to favour relatively cool habitats at the edge of slow-flowing streams that most commonly have mildly acidic water, whereas *N. ugandensis* lives in more

typical *Nothobranchius* pools with alkaline water and higher temperatures. The author found the two species to be syntopic in only one pool out of 20 where *Nothobranchius* were present (Nagy, 2010a).

Figure 2: *Nothobranchius melanospilus* Mbezi River TZN 09-9, wild-caught males photographed in the field.

Figure 3: *Nothobranchius albimarginatus* Mbezi River TZN 09-9, wild-caught male.

Reproductive strategy

Adapted to the conditions of the seasonal biotopes, *Nothobranchius* species have developed an interesting reproductive strategy. The reproductive instinct of the

annual fishes is very strong and spawning activity usually occurs daily throughout their adult lifespan. From the time they reach sexual maturity, they begin to spawn in order to ensure the survival of the popu-

Figure 4: *Nothobranchius ruudwildekampi* Mbezi River TZN 09-9, wild-caught male.

Figure 5: *Nothobranchius luekei* Mbezi River TZN 09-9, wild-caught male.

lation. Generally, the spawning activity is initiated by the female, depending on whether or not she carries mature eggs (Haas, 1976). The natural biotopes are typically turbid because of small suspended particles in the water and submerged objects can be seen through a depth of a few centimeters only. Females generally have drab grey or brown colors which are relatively difficult to spot under such conditions. However, males possess typically striking colors which help the females to find their mates. Once visual contact is made, an initial short display phase will usually occur and spawning will start within a few seconds. When the sexes are in visible distance, they approach each other and males move with particularly rapid and vigorous movements towards the females. The male shows a characteristic darting approach and attempts to drive the female towards the bottom and impress her with extended fins. The male tries to position himself above the female and, for most of

the species, pushing with the lower jaw onto the dorsal surface of her head. One exception to this approach towards the female is represented by members of the *N. microlepis* species group (Figure 6). The male of this group will approach the female from below and push the typical humpback of his head against the belly of the female (Wildekamp and Haas, 1992; Wildekamp, 2004).

A non-receptive female would refuse by escaping and swimming away towards the surface, while a receptive female will move with the male to the substrate. The male then wraps his fins around the female, while pushing her onto, and partially into, the spawning substrate (Figure 7). The body of the male adopts an S-shape while the female forms her anal fin into a conical shape and presses it into the substrate. After a few seconds of trembling movement the pair stays motionless for a second and the female releases a single egg with a rapid jerk movement, while the de-

Figure 6: *Nothobranchius bojiensis* Ewaso Ng'iro KEN 10-1, wild-caught male.

Figure 7: A pair of spawning *Nothobranchius guentheri*. Note how the male wraps his dorsal and anal fins around the female while pressing her down into the substrate. Photograph by A. Terceira (Copyright 2015).

posited egg is simultaneously fertilized by the male. This egg laying sequence can be repeated several times (Haas, 1976).

A somewhat different spawning behaviour can be observed with the species of the subgenus *Aphyobranchius*, as those tend to spawn in mid-levels of the water and the small eggs sink to the substrate. Another species that may also sometimes spawn at mid-water levels is *N. fuscotaeniatus*.

Morphology

Nothobranchius species generally show little intra-specific morphological variation. Most species are 4-7 cm in total length and only a couple of species might reach 10 cm or more (Wildekamp, 2004). The gen-

eral body shape of the males is usually robust, laterally compressed and deep. The greatest body depth will usually be just in front of the pelvic fin, whereas greatest body width is at the position of the pectoral fin base. Dorsal and ventral profiles of the body are convex. Males possess large and rounded dorsal and anal fins that are positioned behind the mid-length of the body. The body shape and the position of the fins are typical for fishes that are generally poor swimmers over long distances but allow them to initiate movement rapidly and swim quickly over short distances. The predatory *N. ocellatus* has dorsal and anal fins that are set even more posteriorly than other members of the genus, which allows

faster movements when chasing prey (Figure 8). Another distinctive group is represented by members of the subgenus *Aphyobranchius* which have a larger anal fin, and a dorsal fin that is positioned more posteriorly, as an adaption to surface-dwelling behaviour (Figure 5).

Females of *Nothobranchius* species are slightly smaller than the males. Their bodies are usually less laterally compressed and more slender than those of the males. They possess a triangular anal fin with a rounded tip, and the central rays are longer and more rigid. Dorsal and anal fins are positioned more posteriorly than in males.

Phenotypic variations

Nothobranchius species are sexually highly dichromatic with the male usually being very colorful while the female will

usually have dull grey-brown coloration. In some species color polymorphism exists. One of the most typical cases is when males of some species exhibit either red and blue, or red and yellow color morphs, such as with *N. eggersi* or *N. korthausae*, respectively (figures 9 and 10). The two color morphs of *N. eggersi* seem to appear sympatrically in the same general area but not syntopically (i.e. not in the same habitat), whereas the color forms of *N. korthausae*, including intermediate forms, might sometimes, but not always, occupy the same habitat (Nagy, 2008). In some other cases, the phenotypic variations are restricted to only one component of the color pattern, such as *N. jubbi* having either a red or a blue caudal fin (Nagy, 2009). These phenotypic features seem to be determined by genetic factors.

Figure 8: Abdalla Khamis Muhune, driver and field assistant, holding two 8-inch bags, each containing an adult wild-caught male *Nothobranchius ocellatus*. Location Ruvu River TAN 02-31. Photograph by B.R. Watters (Copyright 2015).

Other differences in male coloration, representing either enhancement or suppression, can be driven by environmental factors or dominance. For example, dominant males of some species might develop

signals in the form of a striking color in the fins, such as a relatively vivid submarginal band to the caudal fin. Subordinate males might show a decrease in color intensity under such conditions.

Figure 9: *Nothobranchius korthausae* Mafia Island TZN 08-2, wild-caught male, yellow phenotype.

Figure 10: *Nothobranchius korthausae* Mafia Island TZN 08-4, wild-caught male, red phenotype.

Diet and feeding habits

Nothobranchius species are generally micropredators feeding on small aquatic crustaceans, worms, insect larvae and other zooplankton (Polačik and Reichard, 2010). Live food is especially important due to their high energy consumption during the fast growth period and high reproductive effort. One species, *N. ocellatus* has evolved as a large predator (Figure 10) and can always be found with at least one, and often several, other *Nothobranchius* species. In particular, it is without exception found syntopically with *N. melanospilus* (Watters, 2009). The members of the *N. microlepis* species group have specially adapted gill rakers that allow them to feed predomi-

Figure 11: *Nothobranchius microlepis* Mnazini KEN 08-8 displaying predatory behavior in the rearing aquarium.

Figure 12: Developed egg of *Nothobranchius chochamandai*.

nantly on small planktonic crustaceans. The author has also on several occasions observed them, under captive conditions, preying on other fish, such as the smaller members in the same aquarium (Figure 11).

Embryonic development

Embryonic development of annual fishes is highly adapted to the seasonal conditions that prevail in the habitats (Peters, 1963; Watters, 2009). The eggs are protected against the harsh conditions of the dry season by having a relatively hard outer shell, the chorion. The shell has a layered structure and the thickened egg wall is highly resistant to the loss of moisture from within, and can even withstand physical pressure to some extent. The full development of the eggs involves a series of developmental stages with intervening rest periods or diapauses (Figure 12). This pattern of embryonic development represents an essential adaptation to the prolonged dry period.

In order to ensure a suitable environment for the development of the eggs, the fish have to deposit them beneath the surface of the substrate and this is achieved by the female forming her anal fin into a conical shape, a chute of sorts, and pressing into the substrate. As a result of the rapid jerk movement of the spawning, as well as

the vigorous fin movements, some substrate material is stirred up from the bottom. These substrate particles would cover the eggs when settling again. Females of some species living in very dry areas have a more elongated anal fin, which allows them to place the eggs at greater depth, and thus protect them better from the heat of the direct sunshine and the desiccation of the upper levels of the substrate.

Not all the eggs develop at the same rate, and this phenomenon helps to offset the unpredictability of the rainfall. Some habitats may dry out quickly again after having received some early precipitation and all the newly-hatched fry would die. However, as the eggs develop at different rates, there will still be an opportunity for a population to be established when the rains continue, thereby ensuring the survival of the population through erratic rainfall conditions or exceptionally long dry periods.

When the rainy season begins, the seasonal habitats are again filled with rain water, and also by a rise in the water table. The temporary biotopes are then quickly inhabited by organisms that are specially adapted to such seasonal conditions and the amazing cycle of life starts again....

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